

**A CASE REPORT: AN AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF SHWITRA
(VITILIGO) WITH SHAMAN CHIKITSA ALONG WITH VIDHA
KARMA**

Dr. Shaista Mansuri*

Post graduate Student, R. A. Podar hospital, Pg Girls Hostel, Worli Mumbai, Maharashtra,
India.

Article Received on 15 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 05 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 16 Feb. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18661242>

***Corresponding Author**

Dr. Shaista Mansuri

Post graduate Student, R. A. Podar
hospital, Pg Girls Hostel, Worli
Mumbai, Maharashtra, India.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Shaista Mansuri*
(2026). A Case Report: An Ayurvedic
Management of Shwitra (Vitiligo) with Shaman
Chikitsa Along with Vidha Karma. World
Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(4), XX-
XX.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.

INTRODUCTION

In *ayurveda*, skin disease is explained under *adhyay kushtharoga adhyay*, the diseases *shweta kushta* or *shwitra* are characterized by whitish discoloured patches on body.

Vitiligo is acquired hypo melanosis characterized by progressive loss of melanocyte. Vitiligo can affect all age groups with majority of cases between 20 and 30 years of age. Vitiligo occurs when pigment producing cells die or stop functioning.

The prevalence of vitiligo ranges from 0.5% to 1%. India is considered to have the highest prevalence in world at about 8.8%.

In *ayurveda* the causes for *shwitra* are considered as untruthfulness, ungratefulness, disrespect for the gods, insult of the preceptor, sinful acts misdeeds of past lives and intake of mutually contradictory food are the causative factors of *shwitra*. The fourth layer of *twacha* called *tamra* is involved in a disease.

Vitiligo is multifunctional polygenic disorder with a complex pathogenesis. It is related to both genetic and non-genetic factors. Although several theories have been proposed about the pathogenesis of vitiligo, the precise cause remains unknown.

Some of the theories are autoimmune/ Auto inflammatory theory, deregulated innate immune response, increase in oxidative stress or presence of melanocyte specific cytotoxic T-cells.

This disease is caused by various erroneous dietary habits and life style which ultimately aggravate the *tridoshas* especially *kapha dosha* along with *rasa, rakta, mansa* and *meda*.

Many *ayurvedic* formulations are used for the regeneration of melanocytes in hypopigmented patches among which *bakuchi* is mentioned in *ayurvedic* text.

As *bakuchi* is one of the *dravya* of *agad* as it is mentioned in *eksar gana* of *sushrut* for *sarpa visha* so it acts as *vishaghana dravya* and act against the *visha* (toxin) created by microorganisms.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

- To determine the efficacy of *ayurvedic* treatment in *shwitra* as mentioned in clinical *ayurvedic* text.
- To evaluate the effect of *bakuchi tail, vidha karma* and *shaman chikitsa* in the management of *shwitra* (vitiligo).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A 34yr old male patient came to outpatient department of *Agad Tantra* of our hospital, presenting with complaints of whitish discoloured patches over right leg over backside of ankle with no itching and no burning sensation, patch is of 2×3×2 inch, over a duration of one year with negative family history. There were no associated complaints no history of environment, occupation and related to contact with harmful dietary substances. A detailed history taking and physical examination were carried out.

Examination

General condition of patient was fair, vitals are normal, local and systemic examination reveals that no abnormality detected, bowels are constipated. Micturition is normal and adequate. Appetite is good.

One white patch over back of ankle with no redness, no itching and no burning sensation.

Evaluation of symptoms

Evaluation of lesion are based on the following criteria

- Size (diameter) of patches on ankle was around 2×3×2 Inches.

- Number of patch- one large patch in right ankle
- Colour of patch – white
- Improvement calculated on the basis of VETI scoring method.

Score	0	1	2	3
Number of patches on % of area involved	Absent	1 – 29%	30 – 69%	70 – 100%
Colour	Normal tensity	>50% filling with normal tensity	<50% of filling with pinkish discolouration	White patches
Itching	Absent	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Hypopigmented patches	Absent	Solitary	Segmental	Generalised

Ashtavidha pariksha

Nadi- 82/min

Mala – asamyak

Mutra – 4-6 times /day

Jivha – saam

Shabda – prakrut

Sparsha- anushnasheet

Drik – prakrut

Akruti- madhyam

Samprapti ghatak

Dosha – vata , pitta, kapha

Dushya – rakta, mamsa, meda, and ambu

Adhishthan – bahya rogmarga- twacha

Strotodushti – strotavrodha

Treatment

1. *Bakuchi ghanavati 1-bd*
2. *Krumikuthar rasa 2-bd*
3. *Mahamanjishthadi kwath – 20ml – bd*
4. *Aarogyavardhini vati 2-tds*
5. *Gandhak rasayan 2-tds*
6. Local application of *bakuchi* tail over 7 days
7. *Vidha karma* with *bakuchi* oil after every 7 days .

DISCUSSION

1. *Bakuchi ghana vati*

Bakuchi is known for its kushthagna properties in ayurvedic text. It has anti inflammatory properties and quick healing properties. Bakuchi ghana vati contains shudha bakuchi provide nutrient to skin cells and helps on restoration of cell.

2. *Krumikuthar rasa*

Krumikuthar rasa is used to destroy all types of krumi, it destroys the krumi of intestines and also raktapradoshaj krumi hence used in shwitra.

3. *Mahamanjishthadi kwath*

This is also known for its raktashodhak properties, manjishtha and other ingredients helps twakprasadak, kushthagna and rakta dhatugami. It brings glow to skin and helps to remove discoloration and promotes healing of damaged skin tissues.

4. *Aarogyavardhini vati*

It helps in deepan- pachan of patients agni, though the tridoshas prakop causes the agni mandya, for samprapyi bhang aarogyavardhini is given.

5. *Gandhak rasayan*

Shudha gandhak is the main element of gandhak rasayan and it has several potential uses for skin health. It is rakta shodhak, tyachya and beneficial to skin.

6. *Bakuchi tail*

Bakuchi tail has been used traditionally in the management of shwitra mentioned in ayurvedic texts, bakuchi(psoralia corylifolia) improved the rate of synthesis and quantity of melanin and hence encouraging skin to get improved from previous state.

Local application of bakuchi tail – after application of bakuchi taila exposure of sunlight is necessary because sunlight contains ultra violet rays which alongwith bakuchi taila promote growth of melanocyte migration of stimulation proliferation.

Vidha karma

vidha karma with needle no – 26 is done at the patch of vitiligo and bakuchi tail is applied over the patch so that the absorption of bakuchi tail till the dermis so that the tail can go upto the site of melanocytes and it accelerates the growth of melanocyte, hence the process hastens the treatment of vitiligo.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Regular use of *shaman aushadhi* and *vidha karma* with *bakuchi* oil application minimizes the size and get shrink also changes the color of patches from white to reddish in first visit follow up and reddish to skin colour after few visits.

VETI Score	Before treatment score	After treatment score
Number of patches on % of area involved	1	0

Colour	3	1
Itching	0	0
Hypopigmented patches	1	0
Total	5	1

Before treatment score: 5

After treatment score: 1

CONCLUSION

Shwitra is a *tridoshaj kricha sadhya* (difficult to cure) disorder causing hypopigmentation / depigmentation of skin. The treatment given to patient has encouraged effects over skin. No much complications were observed in patient though vitiligo has limitations in other pathies and it is difficult to cure, though ayurvedic management of vitiligo is one of the most effective therapies and which has less chance of recurrence.

REFERENCE

1. Snehal Neeraj Patil. Multi-Modality Ayurveda Regime in the Management of Childhood Vitiligo w.s.r.to Shwitra: A Case Report. *AYUSHDHARA*, 2023; 10(1): 63-67. <https://doi.org/10.47070/ayushdhara.v10i1.1161>
2. Gupta Amit Kumar Amit Kumar¹, Prasad Mahendra², Meena M S³, EFFECT OF BAKUCHI ON VITILIGO EFFECT OF BAKUCHI ON VITILIGO – A CASE STUDY, *International Ayurvedic Medical Journal*.
3. charak Samhita, pt. Kashi Nath Shastri hindi commentary, chikitsa sthan 7/4-8, chaukhambha Sanskrita sansthan, Varanasi, reprint 2006.
4. Chakradatta, hindi commentary by Dr. Indra Dev Tripathi, kushthachikitsaprakarana 50/57, reprint 2005, chaukhambha sanskrita bhawan, varanasi.

5. Bhav Prakash nighantu, hindi commented by K.C.Chunekar and G.S.pandey, haritakyadivarga, page 123, reprint: 1999, chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi.* M.D. (Ayu) Scholar, P.G. Department of Sharir Kriya, NIA, jaipur.
6. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, edited with Ayurveda Tattva- Sandipika Hindi commentary by Kaviraja Ambhikdutta Shastri, Vol-2, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Reprint-2011, Chapter no: 9/3, pg.no:62.
7. Krumikuthar Rasa <https://sdlindia.com/product/krumikuthar-rasa>
8. Mahamanjishthadi Kadha; <https://sdlindia.com/product/mahamanjishthadi-kadha>.